

PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF WORDPLAY

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The relevance of the present study is connected with the need to interpret the meanings of new language units functioning in modern texts. The novelty of the work is determined by a comprehensive analysis of phraseological neologisms of different degrees of connectedness in the aspect of wordplay, contributing to the expansion of our ideas about the pragmatic interpretation of wordplay neological combinations.

Authors of journalistic texts create new non-standard combinations to nominate various new situations of reality in cases where it is impossible to express them in cases where it is impossible to express their meaning in one word. The exclusive right to create original nominations belongs to famous politicians, scientists, writers, journalists, satirists, actors - all those whose command of the language is professional and authoritative.

The issues of using new word combinations and interpreting their meanings at the present stage of linguistics development are studied using the theoretical basis of neology, phraseology, philosophy, linguopragmatics, psycholinguistics, linguocultural studies, rhetoric, sociolinguistics and linguopolitics.

When analysing new word combinations through meta-linguistic approach it allows us to go beyond the limits of their linguistic research and to include in the object of study the linguistic components that are associated with linguistic components but are not linguistic [1, p. 57].

In modern linguistics, when analysing new words, phraseological expressions and meanings, the most used term is term "neologism" [2, c. 25]. I.V.Skuratov developed the basic criteria for defining a neologism combination (NC):

- 1) a combination that contains a formal neologism;
- 2) a new combination of existing words in the language, possessing characteristics potentially capable of creating a new established unit of the language;

3) a combination obtained as a result of reinterpretation of the usual meaning of an existing linguistic unit of an already existing linguistic unit [3, p. 63-64].

The object of this study are combinations of words formed by the playful technique of verbal decomposition of stable combinations. Verbal decomposition of a stable combination is considered as a linguistic experiment of a creative linguistic personality with semantic combinability with the purpose of marking a new meaning.

With the aim of denoting a new meaning. The game techniques of verbal decomposition of stable combinations are based on the selection of a well-known stable combination and its further recompanisation and its fragment or the whole construction with the help of by means of various types of substitutions, truncations or contaminations based on phonetic or syntactic connection.

In Le Petit Robert's dictionary, a wordplay is a humorous innuendo based on the ambiguity created by words that are phonetically similar but contrast in meaning phonetically similar but contrasting in meaning.

In Russian linguistic, wordplay is considered as a component of the phenomenon of language play, thoroughly studied in the works of E.M. Aleksandrova, O.E.Voronichev, T.A.Gridina, O.V.Zalesova, O.S.Zubkova, E.I.Kumanitsyna, G.V.Rakhimkulova, V.Z.Sannikov, O.A.Shishkareva and others.

The term *wordplay* remains controversial in the scientific literature. As applied to the present work, the closest interpretation of language game is the one developed by E.I.Kumanitsyna as "conscious variation of linguistic signs and transformation of linguistic forms, creating non-trivial new language forms transformation of linguistic forms, creating non-trivial new linguistic units in order to influence the society" [4, 8 p.].

Investigating the model of the mechanism of word play V. S. Vinogradov suggested about its two-component nature, where the first component is the basis, and the second - "result" (a word or word combination) - a "shifter" which becomes a favourable ground for creation of individual-author neologisms. Wordplay occurs only when the "resulta" is realized in speech and mentally correlated with the base, which can be perceived in a wider context or even only implied [5, p. 153-154].

The French lexicologist R. Galisson formulated the notion of verbal palimpsest as an autonomous statement (or its fragment), the result of mental superimposition of a basic utterance and a derived utterance. Where the base

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utterance is a stable expression (proverb, proverb, saying, the title of a book, film, theatre play, etc.), and a derivative is the result of a verbal decomposition of the basic statement. At the same time, the derived utterance retains traces of the presence of the basic utterance, which allows the listener to recognise the original expression. Decomposition is based on a conscious violation of the norm on the basis of phonetic or syntactic (rhythmic) connection [6, p. 45].

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